

Mixed-ligand Complexes of Mercaptobenzimidazoles

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Manuscript received 30 November 1993, accepted 31 May 1994

In continuation of our earlier studies on the coordinating tendencies of substituted benzimidazoles^{1,2}, we report herein the formation constants of ternary complexes of type MAL (where M = Co^{II}, Ni^{II}, Zn^{II}; L = 2-mercaptomethylbenzimidazoles (MEB) or 2-mercaptoethylbenzimidazole (MEB); A = bipyridyl, 1,10-phenanthroline or orthophenylenediamine (OPDA)) determined pH-metrically in 50% (v/v) aqueous ethanol at 30° and *I* = 0.1 M (NaClO₄).

Results and Discussion

The stability of the various ternary metal complexes and the corresponding binary metal complexes have been quantitatively compared in terms of the parameter $\Delta \log K$ which is expressed as

$$\Delta \log K = \log K_{MAL}^{MA} - \log K_{ML}^M$$

$\Delta \log K$ values reflect the ability of the MEB, MMB (secondary ligands) to bind the various M(II)-bipy/phen/OPDA binary complexes relative to the aquo-metal ion. The $\Delta \log K$ values for the various ternary complexes have been calculated (Table 1). In order to obtain precise values of $\Delta \log K$ it is essential that the binary and ternary constants should refer to identical experimental conditions. Hence, acid dissociation constants of all the ligands and their binary formation constants with different metal ions are redetermined in this work at 30°, *I* = 0.1 M (NaClO₄). The data in Table 1 show that $\Delta \log K$ values are negative for all ternary systems investigated. Based on a purely statistical basis, negative values of $\Delta \log K$ are expected since there are more coordinating sites on the aquo-metal ion relative to the binary metal complex. The $\Delta \log K$ values which are more negative or positive, represent destabilisation or stabilisation respectively.

Another parameter, percentage relative stabilisation

(% RS) has been used to measure the relative ease of the formation of mixed ligand complexes which may be defined³ as

$$\% \text{ RS} = \left[\left(\log K_{MAL}^{MA} - \log K_{ML}^M \right) / \log K_{ML}^M \right] \times 100$$

The data in Table 1 indicate that the stabilities of M(II)-bipy-L ternary system are higher than those of M(II)-phen-L and M(II)-OPDA-L systems. The higher stabilities of M(II)-bipy-L and M(II)-phen-L systems compared with those of M(II)-OPDA-L systems may be due to the ability of phen and bipy to form π -bonds as observed by previous workers^{4,5}. The higher stabilities of M(II)-bipy-L than those of M(II)-phen-L may be due to the flexible nature of bipy molecule. The order of stabilities of ternary complexes with respect to metal ions (Zn^{II} > Ni^{II} > Co^{II}) is in agreement with Irving-Williams order. The ternary complexes involving MEB as secondary ligands are more stable than the ternary complexes involving MMB as secondary ligand. This trend could be explained in terms of basicity and ring size. All the primary ligands (A), viz. phen, bipy or OPDA would form five-membered ring upon coordination to metal ions. Similarly, MMB forms five-membered ring while MEB forms six-membered ring with metal ions. The ternary systems involving five- and six-membered rings are more stable than those ternary systems having both five-membered rings^{6,7}. Moreover, the basicity of MEB is more than the basicity of MMB.

Experimental

The ligands MMB and MEB were prepared by the reported method⁸. Other chemicals were of A.R. grade and used as received. The proton-ligand formation constant and metal-ligand formation constant were determined pH-metrically using Irving-Rossotti pH-titration technique⁹. The formation constants of ternary

TABLE 1 – MIXED-LIGAND FORMATION CONSTANTS OF MERCAPTOBENZIMIDAZOLES

Temp. = 30 ; Medium = 50% (v/v) aq. ethanol. $I = 0.1 M$ (NaClO₄)

	Bipy-MEB			Bipy-MMB		
	$\log K_{MAL}^{MA}$	$\Delta \log K$	% RS	$\log K_{MAL}^{MA}$	$\Delta \log K$	% RS
Co ^{II}	6.83	-1.22	-15.15	8.64	-1.67	-16.19
Ni ^{II}	7.85	-1.06	-11.89	7.80	-1.59	-16.93
Zn ^{II}	8.24	-0.90	-9.82	8.20	-0.90	-9.84
	OPDA-MEB			OPDA-MMB		
Co ^{II}	6.46	-1.59	-19.75	6.72	-1.97	-19.10
Ni ^{II}	7.48	-1.43	-16.04	7.44	-1.95	-20.76
Zn ^{II}	8.02	-1.14	-12.44	7.74	-1.40	-15.31
	Phen-MEB			Phen-MMB		
Co ^{II}	6.58	-1.47	-18.26	8.44	-1.87	-18.13
Ni ^{II}	7.63	-1.28	-14.36	7.59	-1.80	-19.16
Zn ^{II}	8.14	-1.02	-11.13	8.10	-1.04	-11.37

MMB : $pK_{SH} = 9.47$, $pK_{NH} = 4.59$; $\log K_1 = 10.31$ (Co^{II}), 9.39 (Ni^{II}), 9.14 (Zn^{II}).MEB : $pK_{SH} = 10.16$, $pK_{NH} = 5.03$; $\log K_1 = 8.05$ (Co^{II}), 8.91 (Ni^{II}), 9.16 (Zn^{II}).

systems have been evaluated by the method of Ramamurthy and Santappa¹⁰. The pH-metric readings (B) in 50% (v/v) aqueous ethanol media were corrected¹¹. All calculations were performed using the experimental data based on the trends in the titration curves on a CASIO-PB-110 personal computer with the aid of suitable material balanced equations^{9,10}

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